

INTRODUCTION

Describing Parkinson's Disease (PD) within a contemporary cohort, followed longitudinally with both clinical and biological data, can offer valuable insights into the evolving course of PD under current management paradigms. The Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) has been following participants prospectively for approximately 13 years, enabling this type of analysis. An integrated biological and clinical staging system (NSD-ISS) has been proposed, based on biological markers such as synuclein seed assay positivity in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF-SAA+) and dopamine transporter (DAT) binding deficits [1].

METHODS

We analyzed longitudinal data from $n=344$ participants enrolled in the sporadic PD cohort in PPMI who met neuronal synuclein disease criteria and were recruited before 2020. Participants were assessed with comprehensive motor/non-motor scales. Time to milestone analyses were performed as described in Brumm et al [2]. Report Generated on Data Submitted as of January 2, 2024.

RESULTS

At baseline, distribution of NSD staging in the cohort was: 2b=79 (23%); 3=230 (67%); 4=35 (10%). There were stage dependent differences across motor and non-motor domains, event those not used as stage anchors (**Table 1**). DAT binding differed among NSD stages at baseline, with lower binding in NSD Stage 4. A higher percentage of participants in NSD Stage 4 presented neurofilament light chain (NfL) ≥ 19.05 pg/mL (**Table 2**).

At 11 years data were available for 153 participants and 35 participants (10%) had died. Functional impairment progressed over time (**Figure 1**).

Of 153 participants, $n=77$ (59%) were categorized with normal cognition.

All DAT binding measures worsened over time, with mean [SD] age/sex expected lowest putamen SBR of 0.24 [0.09]. Serum NfL consistently increased over 5-year follow-up. The percentage of participants with a serum NfL ≥ 19.05 pg/mL also consistently increased over 5 years (32% by year 5). No other biofluid markers showed a consistent trajectory over time

CONCLUSION

We describe the largest cohort of biologically characterized SPD participants with >10 years follow up. There was significant baseline NSD stage heterogeneity in the cohort despite all being recruited as *de novo* PD.

Baseline NSD-ISS predicts time to death, disability, postural instability and cognitive decline. Biological underpinnings of stage heterogeneity and the role of co-pathology need to be further explored. The NSD-ISS provides the framework to do so. These results have significant implications on selection of participants and study designs testing disease modifying interventions.

REFERENCES

1. Simuni T, Chahine LM, Poston K, et al. A biological definition of neuronal alpha-synuclein disease: towards an integrated staging system for research. *Lancet Neurol.* 2024 Feb;23(2):178-90.
2. Brumm MC, Siderowf A, Simuni T, et al. Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative: A Milestone-Based Strategy to Monitor Parkinson's Disease Progression. *J Parkinsons Dis.* 2023;13(6):899-916

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Table 1. Baseline Demographic and clinical characteristics

	SAA + (N = 344)	Stage 2b (N = 79)	Stage 3 (N = 230)	Stage 4 (N = 35)	p-Value
Age (years)	62.4 (33.7, 84.9)	61.1 (37.0, 77.5)	62.7 (33.7, 84.9)	63.4 (39.2, 77.3)	0.424
Sex, Female n (%)	119 (35%)	28 (35%)	76 (33%)	15 (43%)	0.515
Education Category, <12 Years n (%)	21 (6%)	5 (6%)	15 (7%)	1 (3%)	0.880
Race, White n (%)	317 (92%)	73 (92%)	210 (92%)	34 (97%)	0.527
Hispanic or Latino Ethnicity, n (%)	7 (2%)	1 (1%)	6 (3%)	0	0.851
Time from Diagnosis to Baseline (years)	0.3 (0.0, 3.0)	0.4 (0.1, 2.1)	0.3 (0.0, 3.0)	0.6 (0.1, 2.5)	0.008
UPSIT Percentile	5.5 (1.0, 96.5)	7.0 (1.0, 78.5)	5.3 (1.0, 91.5)	5.0 (1.0, 96.5)	0.613
MDS-UPDRS Part I	5.0 (0.0, 23.0)	2.0 (0.0, 10.0)	5.0 (0.0, 13.0)	13.0 (4.0, 23.0)	< 0.001
MDS-UPDRS Part II	5.0 (0.0, 22.0)	2.0 (0.0, 2.0)	6.0 (1.0, 13.0)	14.0 (3.0, 22.0)	< 0.001
MDS-UPDRS Part III (OFF)	20.0 (4.0, 51.0)	14.0 (4.0, 40.0)	21.0 (6.0, 51.0)	26.0 (13.0, 42.0)	< 0.001
MDS-UPDRS Total Score (OFF)	31.0 (7.0, 72.0)	19.0 (7.0, 44.0)	32.0 (12.0, 68.0)	53.0 (34.0, 72.0)	< 0.001
Hoehn and Yahr, n (%)					
1	153 (44%)	55 (70%)	90 (39%)	8 (23%)	< 0.001
2	191 (56%)	24 (30%)	140 (61%)	27 (77%)	
MOCA Total Score	28.0 (17.0, 30.0)	28.0 (21.0, 30.0)	27.0 (17.0, 30.0)	28.0 (17.0, 30.0)	0.041
Cognitive Categorization*, n (%)					1.000
Normal Cognition	70 (91%)	17 (94%)	45 (90%)	8 (89%)	
Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI)	7 (9%)	1 (6%)	5 (10%)	1 (11%)	
RBD Screening Questionnaire Score	3.0 (0.0, 12.0)	3.0 (0.0, 10.0)	3.5 (0.0, 12.0)	7.0 (2.0, 12.0)	< 0.001
GDS	2.0 (0.0, 14.0)	1.0 (0.0, 14.0)	2.0 (0.0, 11.0)	3.0 (0.0, 12.0)	< 0.001
SCOPA-AUT	8.0 (0.0, 39.0)	6.0 (0.0, 16.0)	9.0 (0.0, 39.0)	14.0 (4.0, 35.0)	< 0.001
Modified Schwab & England,	90.0 (70.0, 100.0)	100.0 (85.0, 100.0)	90.0 (70.0, 100.0)	90.0 (80.0, 100.0)	< 0.001

Unless otherwise specified, median (min, max) are reported

Table 2. Baseline biologic characteristics

	SAA + (N = 344)	Stage 2b (N = 79)	Stage 3 (N = 230)	Stage 4 (N = 35)	p-Value
DATscan imaging measures					
Age/Sex-Expected Lowest Putamen SBR	0.31 (0.06, 0.73)	0.35 (0.18, 0.72)	0.30 (0.06, 0.73)	0.28 (0.10, 0.71)	0.003
Mean Striatum Binding,	1.36 (0.31, 2.59)	1.52 (0.84, 2.59)	1.33 (0.31, 2.52)	1.30 (0.71, 2.36)	< 0.001
Fluid Biomarkers					
Serum NfL, pg/mL	11.4 (2.5, 76.6)	11.5 (2.5, 46.6)	11.3 (2.8, 32.5)	13.5 (4.1, 76.6)	0.639
CSF t-tau/A-beta 1-42 ratio	0.18 (0.10, 0.72)	0.18 (0.11, 0.39)	0.18 (0.10, 0.69)	0.19 (0.13, 0.72)	0.276
CSF p-tau/A-beta 1-42 ratio	0.02 (0.01, 0.07)	0.02 (0.01, 0.04)	0.02 (0.01, 0.07)	0.02 (0.01, 0.07)	0.422
CSF A-beta 1-42 \leq 683 pg/mL (A+), n (%)	108 (32%)	23 (30%)	69 (31%)	16 (47%)	0.141
CSF p-tau \geq 13 pg/mL (T+), n (%)	166 (49%)	35 (45%)	112 (49%)	19 (54%)	0.678
Serum NfL \geq 19.05 pg/mL (N+), n (%)	44 (14%)	10 (14%)	25 (12%)	9 (30%)	0.027

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Figure 1. NSD Stage by visit.

Figure 2. Time to reaching milestones.

